

THEORETICAL FEATURES OF EXTRALINGUISTIC PROBLEMS IN THE TRANSLATION OF POPULAR SCIENTIFIC TEXTS

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Abstract. *Nowadays, it is no exaggeration to say that the translation of scientific texts from an extralinguistic point of view and the exchange of scientific and technical information is of great importance for the activity of the field of science. It is very important for the translator of scientific and popular texts to have professional qualifications and to work with special dictionaries to convey information as accurately as possible from the original. In this study, scientific theoretical aspects of extralinguistic problems in the translation of scientific texts were studied. In addition, it is suggested that the translator should have broad specialized knowledge as well as world knowledge to overcome extralinguistic problems in the translation process. In addition, the translator must remember that the more effort or participation in the translation, the better the result.*

Keywords: *theoretical aspect, popular scientific style, extralinguistic features, translation, translation process, scientific technical writing.*

A translator draws on all kinds of knowledge while translating, and such knowledge falls broadly under two types: linguistic and extralinguistic¹. In addition, s/he must be equipped with translation methodology, knowledge and skills involving problem identification, problem-solving, decision-making, subject research skills, etc. A translator's competence might also involve self-concept, aptitude and personality, attitudes and affective factors, translation effort, understanding of translation, etc. Moreover, since these components of translator competence appear to complement each other, a translator who is lacking in one component or another can resort to other component(s) to compensate for that lack.

As in the case of any other type of translation, there are certain requirements, norms, and features of the translation of scientific and technical texts. In general, the translation cannot be a free presentation or literal interlinear of the original, but partially in the text of the translation, it is possible to use such methods of translation. For instance, in the case when a literal translation accurately and clearly conveys the meaning of the original and at the same time corresponds to the usage of the Russian language, or vice versa, when the transfer of meaning is possible only with a complete transformation of the phrase. The main condition is the transmission of the undistorted meaning of the original. As for the translation of scientific and technical style texts, According to Yu.I. Lashkevich "A translation should not only correctly reflect the meaning of the original text, but also correspond to a form that is as close as possible to the form of the original". The quality of such a translation depends on the translator's knowledge of the topic of the text and the language. Correspondence with the style of scientific and technical texts is also an important aspect of adequate translation. Each language has its own characteristics of different styles, and all of them can both coincide and differ in languages.

The following is a list of the general extralinguistic features of scientific and technical writing:

- strict logic of presentation;
- information content;

- monologic type of speech;
- objectivity (argumentation, motivation);
- orientation to logical perception;
- terminology (general technical, intersectoral or highly specialized).

Additionally, scientific and technical writing possesses the following characteristics:

- abbreviations, which, as a rule, are deciphered during translation;
- frequent use of complex prepositions;
- use of words of Romance origin;
- the presence of attributive complexes;
- extended syntactic constructions

The main role of extralinguistic factors that have a significant impact on the process and outcome of translation activity is one of the most pressing issues in the theory of translation field in recent years. The role of extralinguistic factors of a speech act in the general sense of individual elements of the text is that they (extralinguistic factors) largely remove the ambiguity (both lexical and grammatical or structural) of language units. By using extralinguistic factors, the translator can reach the degree of the most suitable equivalent. It is impossible to study speech in isolation from the speaker as a representative of a certain culture, a certain social group, and as a person with his own subjective characteristics: “Language is always inseparable from a person who cannot be thought outside of his subjective judgments and subjective perceptions”.

L. S. Barkhudarov noted translation as “the process of transforming a speech work in one language into a speech work in another language while maintaining an unchanged content plan”. This definition is certainly correct. However, translation is a complex activity, and the essence of translation is the process of interlingual and intercultural communication. In addition to that, “translation is not only an interaction of languages, but also an interaction of cultures”. Therefore, the absolute and complete equivalence of translation is basically not achievable. The aim of translation as an intercultural communication should be cultural equivalence.

Different cultures, different personalities, different ways of thinking, different kinds of literature, different epochs, different levels of development, different traditions and attitudes always collide in translation, and besides the fact that linguistic factors directly affect translation activity, the extralinguistic factors listed above also have a strong influence on her. Due to the fact that there are extra-linguistic factors in two languages and there are differences in the cultures of different peoples, it is absolutely necessary for the translator, as a participant in a kind of speech act, to have certain extra-linguistic information.

During the formation of translation theory, the attention of researchers was focused on some intralinguistic factors. The problems of translatability and equivalence have been posed and considered mainly within the framework of linguistics. The connection between translation and linguistics is undeniable, but this does not mean at all that translation can be performed without taking into account such extralinguistic factors as the history of the people, their culture, social, geographical, and ethnic conditions, and contacts with other peoples.

Moreover, the essence of translation is the process of interlinguistic and intercultural communication. The translation is not only an interaction of languages but also an interaction of cultures. Different nations have different cultures, different personalities, different ways of thinking, different literature, different epochs, different levels of development, different

traditions and attitudes, and besides the fact that linguistic factors directly affect translation activities, the extralinguistic factors listed above also have a strong influence on her. Therefore, the absolute and complete equivalence of the translation is basically not achievable.

The most important problem of literary translation is extralinguistic factors, that is, phenomena that lie outside the structure of the language itself, although they are directly related to it. According to L. S. Barkhudarov “Language and translation” noted that having defined the theory of translation as a linguistic discipline, it is necessary to establish its place among other branches of language science.

In consequence, scientific and technical texts and popular science texts also belong to the scientific style. They have both similar and different features, there is an erroneous opinion that the popular science substyle of texts is easier to translate due to the seemingly simplified structure at first glance. But due to differences in communicative purpose, the means of expression used in such texts create additional difficulties for translation. Their main task is to convey cognitive information to the recipient, which, as a rule, is given in large volumes in scientific texts. In addition, a characteristic feature of such texts is the heterogeneity of the vocabulary used in them. For example, to denote special concepts from aviation and space fields, they resort to common vocabulary, as well as to industry and highly specialized terms, professionalism, jargon, and borrowings.

In conclusion, the theoretical aspects of the extralinguistic features of the original and the similarity and uniqueness of the translation of the texts in the scientific-popular style can be explained by the opinions of the above scientists. It is important to study the process of translating various scientific sources into two languages. Therefore, it is important for us to identify and solve the main extralinguistic features of scientific and popular texts, as well as the problems that arise in the translation of such texts. First of all, we believe that it is difficult to achieve any goal in practice without scientific research on the theoretical aspects of translation. Therefore, by analyzing a number of popular scientific translations into two languages, it is possible to come to a certain practical value.

REFERENCES

1. Ginzburg, R.S. A Course in Modern English Lexicology. R.S. Ginzburg, S.S Khidekel, G.Y Knyazeva, A.A. Sankin. – M. : Vyssaja Skola, 1979. P. 271.
2. <http://www.practica.ru/Articles/scientific.htm>
3. Laukkanen, J. “Affective and Attitudinal Factors in Translation Processes,” Target 8, 1996. P. 257- 274
4. Бархударов, Л.С. Язык и перевод. М. : Международные отношения, 1975. С. 240.
5. Бархударов, С.Г. Проблемы языка, науки, техники, логические, лингвистические и исторические аспекты терминологии. С. Г. Бархударов. - М. : Наука, 1970. С. 356.
6. Угнаев, В.С. Специфика функционирования немецкой авиационной и космической лексики в текстах немецкой общественнополитической прессы [Текст]/ В.С. Угнаев// Известия РГПУ им.А.И. Герцена. – Санкт-Петербург : РГПУ им. А.И. Герцена, 2014. С. 89-94
7. Ibragimov, X., & Sh, A. (2008). *Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik). T.: Fan va texnologiya, 288.*

8. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Креативность как одна из характеристик личности будущего педагога. *Наука, образование и культура*, (3 (27)), 44-46.
9. Хонимкулова, М. Х. К., & Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Необходимость изучения иностранных языков: теория и практика. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (27 (39)), 80-83.
10. Ibragimovich, I. K. (2020). Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system. *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education*, 1, 6-15.
11. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Теоретические аспекты социально-психологической адаптации студентов-первокурсников к обучению в вузе. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (26 (75)), 12-16.
12. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). Коммуникативная компетентность как механизм профессионального саморазвития будущего педагога. *Проблемы педагогики*, (2 (34)), 7-10.
13. Ibragimov, X., & Abdullaeva, S. H. (2008). Theory of pedagogy. *Science and Technology*.
14. Ибрагимов, Х. И. (2020). Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (7 (54)), 74-75.
15. Ibragimovich, X. I. (2021). O 'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA KREDIT-MODUL TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO 'LLASHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 209-214.
16. Ibragimov, X. I., Yo'ldoshev, U. A., & Bobomirzayev, X. (2009). "Pedagogik Psixologiya" O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent.
17. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых. *Academy*, (10 (49)), 39-41.
18. Атауллаев, Ф. Ф. У., & Ибраимов, Х. И. (2019). Понятие профессионально-коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей в психолого-педагогических исследованиях. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (1 (42)), 70-74.
19. Ibragimovich, I. K. (2018). Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (27 (39)), 78-80.
20. Ibragimovich, I. K., Kholboevna, I. F., Amrilloevich, I. A., & Rakhmonovich, U. S. (2021). PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT. *湖南大学学报 (自然科学版)*, 48(12).
21. Ибрагимов, Х. И. (2021). ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1 (80)), 608-611.
22. Ibragimov, X. I., & Salimova, Z. K. (2021). Relevance of english language science and teaching structure. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 883-887.
23. Ibragimov, X. I., & Salimova, Z. K. (2021). Intensive in teaching english characteristics of application of methods. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1588-1594.
24. Rahmanovich, O. A., Yusufovich, E. H., Dilshodqizi, S. S., Almasovna, S. A., & Ibragimovich, H. I. (2020). Linguistic features of compound words in english and Uzbek languages. *European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine*, 7(2), 925-932.
25. Bahtiyorova, F. H. USING FOLK LITERATURE IN THE PRIMARY ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS.

26. Ибраимов, Х. И. (2018). НЕЙРОПЕДАГОГИКА КАК НОВОЕ ПРИКЛАДНОЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY* (pp. 6-10).
27. Ibragimovich, I. H., & Ghazzali, I. Increasing the Classical Activity of Future Teachers as a Pedagogical and Psychological Problem. *JournalNX*, 98-102.